

Biomimicry Aesthetics

A Real-Time Generative Graphical System – “Sensitive Floral” Mimic the Reactive Characteristics of Mimosa Pudica

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ABSTRACT

"Sensitive Floral" is an interactive, generative artwork that ventures into the exploration of a unique generative system, biomimetically emulating the reactive behaviors of the Mimosa pudica plant. By synthesizing the complexity of fractal tree data structures with the Cellular Automata (CA) mechanisms of grid computations, the artwork mirrors nature's adaptive and responsive traits. This approach demonstrates the potential of generative design, organize coding rules and geometric relationships within parameters to shape biomimetic aesthetics. The interaction allows users to initiate a ripple of movement by simply touching the screen, triggering large numbers of changes across thousands of leaves, as like the group leaf movements observed in Mimosa pudica. This subtle yet intricate movement of digital flora not only reflects the beauty of natural phenomena but also opens further opportunities for expression in shape and movement behavior, brings a subtle immersive experience in the field of techno art and human-computer interaction.

CCS CONCEPTS

- **Applied computing** → Arts and humanities → Media arts
- **Human-centered computing** → Interaction design → Interaction design process and methods → Scenario-based design
- **Computing methodologies** → Computer graphics → Graphics systems and interfaces → Perception

KEYWORDS

Generative Design, Artificial Life Art, Cellular Automata, Grid Computing, Fractal Tree

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1 Introduction

In the realm of biomimetic media [1], there has been a significant rise in simulations that effectively combine biomimetic traits with computational systems. These computational systems are designed to interact with external audiences through sensors. Their goal is to replicate the sensory experiences of biological entities in their interactions with humans. Concepts from biologically inspired computing, such as generative design and agent mechanisms, have been actively explored to create artistic expressions of artificial life [2].

Building upon recent advancements in this field, we are fascinated by the integration of generative art with complex systems. We draw inspiration from a variety of sources, such as the aesthetics of fractal trees [3], the behavior patterns of cellular automata [4], the principles of swarm behavior [5], and the manipulation of emergent behaviors in morphogenetic systems [6]. By integrating these elements, we seek to explore new possibilities in generative art. This interdisciplinary approach utilizes the inherent beauty of natural phenomena and complex systems, resulting in innovative and aesthetically captivating artworks.

The intent of this study is two-fold: to expand the visual expressions and presentation forms of generative art, and to investigate the intricate dynamics of art, data constructs, emergent behavior, and adaptive mechanisms. Through this scholarly endeavor, we aim to offer a comprehensive perspective on the potential developments at the intersection of art and complexity science, with a focus on data visualization. This approach highlights the potential of visualizing data to reveal the complex and dynamic nature of art and its interactions.

Building on my previous work with the Hybrid Dandelion [7], which utilizes fractal trees, recursion, and symmetry to create intricate floral patterns, the Sensitive Floral piece ventures further. In this creative endeavor, I drew inspiration from the cellular automata model, integrating its grid computing framework with a binary tree-based data structure. This combination fosters the emergence of adaptive interactive relationships among neighboring branches, including parent branches within the iteration hierarchy,

sibling branches with shared iteration relations, and child branches in subsequent iterations.

Through the utilization of this binary tree structure, we can initiate internal, localized communication and information exchange, triggered by external stimuli. This, in turn, elicits a diffusive cellular motion response, effectively mimicking the dynamic collective reactions observed in the leaves of *Mimosa pudica* [8].

In essence, this research embarks on an interdisciplinary exploration that integrates the disciplines of fractal trees, cellular automata, swarm behaviors, and morphogenetic systems within the realm of generative art. Drawing from the intrinsic elegance of natural phenomena and complex systems, our aim is to curate innovative and thought-provoking artistic works. This study not only seeks to expand the scope of generative art but also to explore the complex interactions among art, data structures, and emergent dynamics. Through this investigative lens, we strive to provide comprehensive insights into the exciting and challenging frontier at the intersection of art and complex data visualization.

2 Implementation

2.1 Generative Graphical System

This work is a real-time, user-interactive graphic generation system developed using Processing software. It instantly detects which branch of the tree structure on the touch screen is triggered by external stimuli from the audience. The system then employs the Cellular Automata (CA) mechanism to calculate and determine the rotational degrees of shrinking behavior between branches. These calculations are immediately applied to the graphic generation system, altering the overall appearance of the flower in real-time.

When a user interacts by touching the virtual flower, the system triggers corresponding curling actions based on the cellular automata mechanism within the fractal tree data structure. The flower responds to various stimuli with unexpected formations, offering a complex range of expressions beyond simple opening and closing. This interactivity invites viewers to explore the flower's form and reactions in their own unique way, highlighting an elegant process of gradual transformation (see as Figure 1).

Figure 1: This image showcases the recorded real-time

interaction scene with audience at SIGGRAPH Asia 2023 Art Gallery (<https://vimeo.com/899765149>)

2.2 Shaping Flower Graphics

The flower shaping heavily employs the recursion mathematical mechanism. Through a set of geometric relationship designs, a concept like cell division is used to grow the next branch. In the iteration process, two characteristics emerge: (1) the development of an organizational relationship of length and angle between lines that presents an organic gradient sense, and (2) the development of movable joints between lines that can display activity for subsequent imitation of the *Mimosa pudica* motion cell mechanism, demonstrating dynamic deformations "Close".

Figure 2: The dandelion-like generative graphics display as a growing, blossoming and morphology processes in animation as nature expression (<https://vimeo.com/947434584>)

2.2.1 Recursion Structure in Making Organic Shape. The rules of recursion are used to mimic biological cell division to generate self-similar sub-branches. In the growth of branches, in addition to a main trunk line, two lines at the start and end points respectively present the image of fluff, displaying biomimicry.

2.2.2 Symmetry in Recursion Structure Making Floral Images. In the iteration within recursion, an axis of symmetry is used, with the same geometric calculation relationship to develop branches in both left and right directions. This way, a tree branch relationship is developed from a single line, and a biomimetic beauty representing flower imagery is developed from it.

2.2.3 Parameter Design for Making Biomimetic Aesthetics Representation. In this generative system, minute adjustments in the rules and parameter contents of recursion can bring about comprehensive impact changes to the overall shape. I developed 14 parameters as the data-driven graphic interface, which include geometric relationships, visual presentation transparency, line thickness, and relative relationships of iterations. Using this method, I shaped aesthetically pleasing biomimetic forms.

2.3 Dynamical Reactive Floral Behavior

In existing research, it has been found that the pulvinar cells at the base of *Mimosa pudica*'s leaves propagate electrical and chemical signals in response to external stimuli, leading to a chain reaction of leaf movement in adjacent cells [4]. To implement this interlinking characteristic, I employ the computational mechanism

of Cellular Automata (CA), both for aesthetic representation and user sensation, within the tree structure's relationships.

2.3.1 Developing a Method of Communication with Neighboring Units in Tree. In Processing's existing fractal tree data structure for image generation, the generation sequence of branches and leaves does not comply with the iteration layer numbering system. Therefore, I have developed a new numbering system that enables each cell to identify its iteration layer and find corresponding relationships with adjacent branches (including the parent branches in the previous iteration layer, sibling branches in the same iteration relationship, and child branches in the next iteration relationship).

2.3.2 Designing Local Communication Mechanisms Driven by Cells for Branch Movement. Each cell is programmed with a mechanism that allows for local communication with neighboring cells in sequence. This communication process induces the contraction state (bend angle) between cells in the branches. The rate of contraction varies depending on the iteration layer. In addition, I have also set up a mechanism for reopening leaves.

Figure 4: Demonstrates the basic sensitive behavior that implement in a binary fractal tree structure through grid computational mechanism.

<https://vimeo.com/860485410>

Figure 5: Demonstrates a biomimetic representation of responsive behaviors in the triggered interaction with Sensitive Floral. <https://vimeo.com/860415773>

3 Future Works

This work provides a method of delving into recursion mechanisms to develop biomimetic creations. By combining the applications of the fractal tree and grid computation, it fosters the development of computational aesthetics and tactile interaction within graphical applications and expressions. The methodology of creation process revealed significant opportunities for expression in shape and movement behavior development based on the current state of iteration layers. Beyond graphical applications, future works will endeavor to explore more possibilities for shape-changing interface sensation expression, endowed by biomimetic computation, through altering tangible interfaces.

This work mixes the joy of touch from physical, with the from extraction and grid computation of information, and the adaptive behavior of complex systems in digital, to develop the expression in generative art. In further, I will also interested apply graphical content and discover novel aesthetics from this generative system, use robotic calligraphic drawing to achieve unusual aesthetics in this constructed system, develop new processes to execute strokes and lines path from digital to physical. Through the management of operating parameters, program logic and data structure, the processing path can be adjusted and the cooperation with specific drawing tools can be adjusted. Development of the end effector will focus on demonstrating specific calligraphy techniques such as strokes, transparency, and creating mechanisms with specific processing paths and force expressions. It is integrated with I/O interface control to generate processing power as performance. With these two projects, will allow audiences to rethink how the mixed culture of virtual and real worlds can bring us new thinking in expanded animation.

Figure 5: The extended undergoing project is using robotic calligraphic drawing, to explore more stork aesthetics from digital to physical.

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